

LEARNING STYLES IN ENGLISH

Yangiboyeva Mushtariybanu Shoymardon qizi
Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy
Faculty of Philology Foreign language and literature
<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8398135>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th September 2023

Accepted: 29th September 2023

Online: 30th September 2023

KEY WORDS

Learning styles, teaching styles, writing, learning process.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to explain the many types of teaching methods used in English classes. It seems hard to alter each student's preferred learning method in the classroom because pupils learn in a variety of ways. The post aims to improve our learning habits while avoiding some issues and faults.

Learning styles have a direct or indirect impact on the teaching and learning process. Different thinkers and experts in education have each provided their own definition of learning styles. They consider this to be a crucial idea that needs to be researched. Understanding how learners differ and how they are similar to one another in terms of learning is made easier by the concept of style. There are numerous ways to define learning style. Rita Dunn created the first "learning style" concept in 1960. Recently, the idea of "learning style" has become very influential in the field of education. Learning preferences, in the words of Kefee, "are distinctive cognitive, affective, and physiological traits that serve as relatively stable indicators of how learners perceive, interact with, and respond to the learning environment." [4]. According to Desire (2019), there are four primary categories of learners, and this is supported by the VARK model of learning styles. Visual, auditory, reading and writing preferences, and kinesthetic are the four main categories. The learning styles paradigm developed by Dunn and Dunn (1989) includes visual, auditory, kindergarten, global analytical, impulsive, reflective, individual, and group.

visual students. These are students who like visual learning methods. Charts, diagrams, graphs, maps, and other visual or graphically based materials that appeal to the sense of sight are crucial in the learning environment. Videos, PowerPoint presentations, and other forms of media are required to support the learning of visual learners.

Aural and auditory learners. These are the students that prefer lectures that focus on the auditory sense. People with hearing loss can learn in their environments through spoken words during lectures, recordings, and discussions.

Readers and writers. This set of learners learns best when they read and record what they have read on paper or a board. Dictionary, Internet, PowerPoint, written responses, and text signs are some of their preferred resources.

physical learners. This group gains knowledge by taking part in the activities included in the learning process. Demonstrations, simulations, movies, and case studies are all used as teaching methods in this group [1].

Learning styles can be broadly divided into the following three groups: cognitive, personality (psychology), and sensory. Kolb's model of learning styles, Ehrman and Leavers' construct, analytical/global, field dependent/field independent, impulsive/reflective, and learning styles are all included under cognitive. Extroverted/introverted, random-intuitive/concrete sequential, and closure-oriented/open orientated are some examples of personality learning styles. Sensation 242 Learning styles can be further broken down into three sub-types: visual, tactile/kinesthetic, and auditory (Hawkar Akram Awla, Learning Styles and Their Relation to Teaching Styles, Dornyei, 2005; Oxford, 2001). Only those learning styles that will be discussed in the research phase are explained in the section that follows.

Sensing (sequential) versus intuitive (random). Imaginative, reflective, and internal memory-based sources of information are preferred by intuitive learners. They enjoy coming up with novel hypotheses and possibilities and think in futuristic, non-sequential, and large-scale ways. Sensing learners, on the other hand, favor knowledge that comes from the senses. They focus on the present and favor facts over speculations. Teachers' direction and instruction are what they want (Felder, 1993; Oxford, 2001). Between analytic vs. global. Global learners focus on the big picture and trust their intuition or make an educated estimate as to what a text's core theme is. Instead of lengthy explanations, they prefer simple answers. In contrast, analytical learners concentrate on using logical analysis and thought to solve issues. They dissect concepts and frequently lay a greater focus on grammar conventions (Dornyei, 2005).

Active as opposed to reflective. Reflective learners comprehend and retain material better by reflecting on it beforehand, while active learners like applying and discussing activities with others while they are being done. Reflective learners love working alone or in pairs while active learners prefer to work in groups (Felder, 1993).

Individual vs. collective choices. Individual students want to work and learn alone independently. On the other side, group-preferring learners prefer to work with others when studying and learning (Dornyei, 2005) [3]. Literature has made use of a variety of terminologies, including learning style, cognitive style, sensory preference, and personality types. While some of these phrases have occasionally been used indiscriminately, others have been separated (Cassidy, 2004). Cognitive styles are described as "an individual's natural, habitual, and preferred way (s) of absorbing, processing, and retaining new information and skills" (Reid, 1995: viii), whereas learning styles are described as "the complex manner, and conditions under which, learners most effectively perceive, process, store, and recall what they are attempting to learn" (James and Gardner, 1995: 20). Learning styles and cognitive types are distinguished by Mortimore (2003). He suggests that learning styles are less constant and are more often evident in terms of the methods that students employ to deal with learning. Conversely, cognitive styles are generally consistent. In contrast to student preferences, learning styles can therefore change over time. Because some authors use the term "cognitive style" as a more generic term that encompasses learning styles (Williamson

and Watson, 2006), [5] it is important to stress that the distinction between the two is not always evident.

The meshing hypothesis is supported by the majority of learning-styles proponents, and it is also assumed in the majority of explanations of how to best implement learning-styles education in the-108 Volume 9—Number 3: Learning Styles education.

For example, they speak of (a) tailoring teaching to "the way in which each learner begins to concentrate on, process, absorb, and retain new and difficult information" (Dunn & Dunn's framework; International Learning Styles Network, 2008), (b) the learner's preferred modes of perception and processing (Kolb's, 1984, 1985, framework), or (c) "the fit between [people's] learning style and the kind of learning experience they face" (Hay Group, n.d., p. 11). It should be noted that the learning-styles hypothesis, as defined here, might be accurate even if the meshing hypothesis is incorrect—for instance, if people who are classified as visual learners sometimes benefit more from verbal instruction or people who are classified as verbal learners sometimes benefit more from visual instruction. In our review, we looked for support for both the more particular meshing hypothesis as well as this broad version of the learning-styles hypothesis. [5].

References:

1. Dunn R, Dunn K (1989). The Dunn and Dunn learning style model of instruction. <https://tracyharringtonatkinson.com/dunn-and-dunnlearning-style/>
2. International Learning Styles Network. (2008). About learning styles. Retrieved August 6, 2009,
3. Oxford, R. (2001) Language learning styles and strategies. In. M. Celce-Murcia, Ed. Teaching English as a second or foreign language (3rd ed.). USA: Heinle & Heinle.
4. UCLA Research Paper (2006). The Dunn and Dunn learning style model of instruction. Retrieved December from www.ethika.dk/eengelesk/news.asp
5. Williamson, MF. & Watson, R. (2006) Learning Styles Research: Understanding How Teaching Should Be Impacted by the Way Learners Learn Christian Education Journal (pp. 27-43).